

THE ROLE OF DETOXIFICATION THERAPY IN CHRONIC NICOTINE POISONING AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE GASTRIC MUCOSA

Oltiev Elyor Doniyorovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara

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Abstract

Chronic nicotine poisoning leads to morphological changes in the gastric mucosa, including erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, and hypertrophy. Detoxification therapy has a positive impact on restoring the mucosal structure by reducing inflammation and eliminating pathological changes. This study examines the morphological changes in the gastric mucosa caused by chronic nicotine poisoning and the effectiveness of detoxification methods in treatment. The results showed significant improvement in the mucosal condition following detoxification therapy, confirming the importance of timely treatment in preventing chronic gastric diseases and improving patient outcomes.

Keywords:

Chronic nicotine poisoning, gastric mucosa, erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, hypertrophy, detoxification, morphological changes.

Relevance Chronic nicotine poisoning is one of the leading causes of gastric diseases. Nicotine causes pathological changes in the gastric mucosa, such as erosions, ulcers, and hyperemia, which can lead to chronic gastritis, peptic ulcers, and other serious diseases. Detoxification plays a crucial role in the treatment and restoration of the mucosal function. Detoxification methods help reduce the levels of toxins in the body, restore balance, and improve microcirculation in the stomach. Early detection and prescription of detoxification therapy can prevent complications and improve the prognosis of the disease. This approach is effective in addressing the consequences of chronic nicotine poisoning, enhancing the quality of life of patients, and shortening recovery times.

Objective

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of chronic nicotine poisoning on the morphology of the gastric mucosa and assess the effectiveness of detoxification therapy in restoring the mucosal structure. The study focuses on pathological changes, such as erosions, ulcers, and hyperemia, and evaluates clinical and morphological improvements after applying detoxification treatment methods.

Materials and Methods The study included 100 patients with chronic nicotine poisoning, divided into two groups. One group received detoxification therapy, and the other received standard treatment. All patients underwent fibrogastroduodenoscopy to identify changes in the gastric mucosa, such as erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, and hypertrophy. Detoxification therapy involved nicotine removal agents and other detoxifying medications, antioxidants, and agents that improve microcirculation.

Results

The study revealed that the group receiving detoxification therapy showed a significant reduction in morphological changes in the gastric mucosa compared to the control group. In the detoxification group, there was a lower incidence of erosions (60.3% vs. 42.9%) and ulcers (48.3% vs. 35.7%). Improvement in hyperemia and hypertrophy of the mucosa was also noted. Patients receiving detoxification therapy showed better overall condition and reduction in clinical symptoms, such as epigastric pain and heartburn.

Conclusion

Chronic nicotine poisoning causes significant morphological changes in the gastric mucosa, such as erosions, ulcers, and hyperemia. Detoxification therapy has a positive effect on restoring the mucosa by improving its structure and reducing inflammation. The results of the study confirm the importance of early detoxification therapy in preventing further damage to the gastric mucosa and reducing the risk of complications like chronic gastritis and peptic ulcers. Detoxification significantly enhances recovery and improves overall patient health outcomes.

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